

How *Ulva lactuca* can influence the impacts induced by the rare earth element Gadolinium in *Mytilus galloprovincialis*? The role of macroalgae in water safety towards marine wildlife

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ABSTRACT

Rare earth elements (REEs) are gaining growing attention in environmental and ecotoxicological studies due to their economic relevance, wide range of applications and increasing environmental concentrations. Among REEs, special consideration should be given to Gadolinium (Gd), whose wide exploitation as a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agent is enhancing the risk of its occurrence in aquatic environments and impacts on aquatic organisms. A promising approach for water decontamination from REEs is sorption, namely through the use of macroalgae and in particular *Ulva lactuca* that already proved to be an efficient biosorbent for several chemical elements. Therefore, the present study aimed to evaluate the toxicity of Gd, comparing the biochemical effects induced by this element in the presence or absence of algae. Using the bivalve species *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, Gd toxicity was evaluated by assessing changes on mussels' metabolic capacity and oxidative status. Results clearly showed the toxicity of Gd but further revealed the capacity of *U. lactuca* to prevent injuries to *M. galloprovincialis*, mainly reducing the levels of Gd in water and thus the bioaccumulation and toxicity of this element by the mussels. The results will advance the state of the art not only regarding the effects of REEs but also with regard to the role of algae in accumulation of metals and protection of aquatic organisms, generating new insights on water safety towards aquatic wildlife and highlighting the possibility for resources recovery.

1. Introduction

Rare earth elements (REEs) represent a group of 17 elements with similar chemical and physical properties, containing about 17% of the elements occurring in the environment (Klinger, 2015; Henderson, 1984). Among REEs, lanthanides are a specific group of elements that possess the same electronic configuration except for the 4f orbitals, which determine their magnetic properties (Sneller et al., 2000). This group of elements includes gadolinium (Gd), one of the most abundant in the Earth crust (6.2 mg/kg) (Greenwood et al., 1997). Despite this fact, it cannot be found as free element in nature, but instead it is contained in several minerals (i.e. bastnaesite, laterite, monazite and loparite) (Pecharsky and Gschneidner Jr, 2019). Gadolinium is the only

lanthanide that has a ferromagnetic behaviour near room temperature, while above 293 K (Curie point - T_c) it acquires paramagnetic characteristics (Dan'kov et al., 1998). Due to these properties, Gd has been employed in the biomedical field as a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agent but also in other industrial areas such as control rods for nuclear reactors and nuclear power implants, garnets for microwave, phosphorous for colour TV tubes, magnets and electronic components (Rogowska et al., 2018), with a pronounced increase in its use since the 80s to the present days (Runge, 2018; Telgmann et al., 2013). The wide utilization of Gd will, therefore, enhance the risk for this element to potentially reach the aquatic environments (Khan et al., 2017). Correlation between the rising levels of Gd in aquatic environments and anthropogenic activities, in particular in densely

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industrialized areas, was firstly reported by Bau and Dulski (1996) and more recently by other authors (among others, Altomare et al., 2020; Barber et al., 2015; Kummerer and Helmers, 2000). For this reason, Gd occurrence in the aquatic ecosystems is expected, through wastewater and industrial discharges, surface run-off and atmospheric deposition (Hatje et al., 2016; Kulaksız and Bau, 2011). Consequently, Gd, directly or indirectly released by human activity, can represent a threat to aquatic environments and inhabiting organisms (Le Goff et al., 2019; Henriques et al., 2019). Recent studies have already demonstrated the toxic impacts induced by Gd towards aquatic organisms, including freshwater and marine bivalves *Dreissena polymorpha* (Pallas, 1771) (Hanana et al., 2017; Xia et al., 2011; Ye et al., 2011), *D. rostriformis bugensis* Andrusov, 1897, *Corbicula fluminea* (Müller, 1774) (Perrat et al., 2017) and *Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lamarck, 1819 (Henriques et al., 2019), but also sea urchins, namely *Paracentrotus lividus* (Lamarck, 1816), *Heliocidaris tuberculata* (Lamarck, 1816) (Martino et al., 2018), *Arbacia lixula* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Sphaerechinus granularis* (Lamarck, 1816) (Gravina et al., 2018; Oral et al., 2017). However, most of the studies have been devoted to freshwater species, and in terms of marine organisms' information is still limited, been focused on gene expression, larval development and sub-cellular alterations.

As a consequence of increasing environmental concentrations and associated threats, as well as REEs economic relevance, water decontamination and the subsequent recovery approaches of REEs have been developed (Anastopoulos et al., 2016). Among the most widely applied methods, such as sorption (Gupta and Sengupta, 2017), liquid-liquid extraction (Xie et al., 2014), chemical precipitation (Zhao et al., 2016) and ion exchange (Anastopoulos et al., 2016; Li et al., 2013), sorption has been considered as one of the most promising methods due to its simplicity, high efficiency and wide-range availability (Anastopoulos et al., 2016; Henriques et al., 2015). As an example, the use of macroalgae has gained attention as a process for water remediation because of their favorable morphology and ubiquitous occurrence, their affinity towards a wide variety of elements and their tolerance to polluted habitats, as well as broad tolerance ranges for salinity and temperature (Costa et al., 2020b, 2020a; Henriques et al., 2015; Zoll and Schijf, 2012). Different studies on bioremediation of elements such as arsenic (As), lead (Pb), mercury (Hg) and cadmium (Cd) and also REEs such as yttrium (Y), europium (Eu) and Gd using macroalgae have been reported (Costa et al., 2020b, 2020a; Ferreira et al., 2020; Henriques et al., 2015; Jacinto et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2004; Pinto et al., 2020; Romera et al., 2007; Zoll and Schijf, 2012). Among all macroalgae species reported in literature, *Ulva lactuca* (Linnaeus, 1753) proved to be efficient in sorbing metals, metalloids and lanthanides (Costa et al., 2020b, 2020a; Ferreira et al., 2020; Henriques et al., 2015; Zoll and Schijf, 2012), showing a great versatility and affinity.

Considering the possible effects of Gd in aquatic ecosystems where it is most likely to be discharged, it is of paramount importance to ensure the environmental safety. The present study aimed to evaluate the toxicity of the Gd-bioremediated water using the macroalgae species *U. lactuca* and to compare its toxicity with Gd-polluted water when no macroalgae are present. The toxicity was evaluated, using the bivalve species *M. galloprovincialis*, by assessing changes on mussels' biochemical performance when exposed to Gd, both in the presence and absence of algae.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental conditions

The Mediterranean mussel *M. galloprovincialis* was selected as a model species for the present experiment, due to its wide employment as bioindicator of pollution as well as its socio-economic relevance (Coppola et al., 2017; Faggio et al., 2018; Henriques et al., 2019; Pagano et al., 2020; Stara et al., 2020).

Animals were collected in February 2020 at the Ria de Aveiro lagoon

(Portugal). Mussels with similar size (5.3 ± 0.7 cm length; 3.0 ± 0.3 cm width) were selected to avoid differences in biological responses. Mussels were transported to the laboratory where they were placed in tanks for depuration and acclimation to laboratory conditions for ten days. During this period, mussels were maintained under constant aeration with artificial seawater (reverse osmosis water with CORAL PRO SALT, Red Sea®) at temperature, pH and salinity values resembling the sampling site conditions (18.0 ± 1.0 °C; 8.1 ± 0.1 , 30 ± 1 , respectively). Seawater was renewed every three days.

U. lactuca seaweed was also collected in February 2020 at the same coastal lagoon. After field sampling, at the laboratory the algae were washed with seawater to remove debris and epibionts and transferred to three aquaria filled with seawater collected from the field (salinity = 28 ± 1) for an acclimation period of one week, under constant aeration. Also in this case seawater was renewed every three days. This procedure was repeated every week during the experimental period of twenty-one days to guarantee fresh algae for weekly medium renewals.

After the acclimation period, mussels and algae were distributed in different aquaria (three aquaria per condition, each one with 3 L of seawater) and the following conditions were tested: control (CTL, clean seawater only with mussels), Algae + Mussels (aquaria with mussels and algae, in the absence or presence of Gd); Mussels (aquaria with mussels in the absence or presence of Gd). A total of sixty mussels were used for this experiment (five mussels per aquarium, fifteen per condition). According to previous studies where living *U. lactuca* was used to remove Gd from seawater (Ferreira et al., 2020), Gd concentration was 50 µg/L while the algal mass was 3 g/L. Commercial Gd standard ("Agilent Technologies" Gadolinium Standard 10,000 µg/mL Gd in 5% HNO₃) was used in the present study (specifications: manufactured in an ISO 9001, ISO Guide 34 facility, and certified to ISO/IEC 17025, with purity confirmed by ICP-MS).

During the experimental period, water and algae were changed every week and the medium conditions re-established, including Gd concentrations and seawater parameters (temperature 18 ± 1.0 °C, pH 8.1 ± 0.1 and salinity 30 ± 1). Throughout the exposure period, the water medium in each aquarium was continuously aerated with a photoperiod of 12 h light: 12 h dark. Due to the COVID-19 situation and the emergency state experienced in March in Portugal, the exposure period lasted for twenty-one days and not twenty-eight days as planned initially.

Along the experimental period, **Blanks** (3 replicates) were also prepared with seawater without algae and mussels but with Gd at the same exposure concentration to evaluate the chemical stability of the element in the water during one-week exposure period. For this purpose, during the exposure period, water samples were collected each week at days 1 (immediately after exposure), 2, 3, 4 and 5 (Table 1). An extra **Algae** condition (algae without Gd and without mussels, 3 replicates) was also prepared to assess the Gd content due to the presence of the algae. In this case water samples were only collected at day-1 of each week, after water renewal (Table 1). Aiming to assess real exposure concentrations water samples from Gd-containing aquaria (**Algae + Mussels**, **Mussels** and **Algae conditions**, Table 1) were taken each week at days 1 (immediately after spiking), 2, 3, 4 and 5 along the experimental period, while water samples from the remaining conditions (**CTL** and **Algae + Mussels**, Table 1) were collected at the first day of each week (after water renewal). Water samples were maintained in glass tubes, acidified with 25 µL of HNO₃ 65% solution, covered with parafilm and stored at 4 °C until analyzed.

During both the exposure and acclimation periods, mussels were fed with Algamac protein plus (150,000 cells/animal) three times per week (the same food amount was also added to the aquaria not containing mussels to maintain equal environmental conditions). Mortality was daily checked, with 100% of survival at the end of the experiment. At the end of the exposure period, mussels were frozen individually and stored at -80 °C. For each individual, the whole soft tissues were homogenized under liquid nitrogen and divided into aliquots (each with 0.5 g fresh weight, FW) for biomarkers analyses and Gd quantification.

Table 1

Gadolinium (Gd) concentrations ($\mu\text{g/L}$) in water samples collected immediately after the beginning of mussels' exposure (1st day), and then daily during the following 4 days, along 21 days of exposure to the following conditions: **CTL** (clean seawater only with mussels); **Algae + Mussels** (aquaria with algae and mussels in the absence of Gd); **Mussels** (aquaria with mussels without algae in the presence of Gd); **Algae + Mussels** (aquaria with algae and mussels in the presence of Gd). Limit of quantification (LOQ) was $5.0 \mu\text{g/L}$. **Gray** conditions represent absence of Gd. **Bold** conditions represent presence of Gd. Significant differences among sampling days for each condition are represented by different lowercase letters.

	1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	4 th day	5 th day
CTL	< 5.0	-	-	-	-
Algae + Mussels	< 5.0	-	-	-	-
Mussels	59 ± 2.4 ^a	43 ± 4.5 ^b	31 ± 8.0 ^c	34 ± 10 ^{b,c}	23 ± 8.7 ^c
Algae + Mussels	45 ± 5.1 ^a	18 ± 1.7 ^b	-	-	15 ± 2.1 ^b
Algae	53 ± 14 ^a	34 ± 2.6 ^a	26 ± 2.2 ^b	24 ± 3.8 ^b	22 ± 0.5 ^b
Blanks	59 ± 1 ^a	45 ± 5.0 ^b	49 ± 15 ^{a,b}	40 ± 8.7 ^b	45 ± 7.4 ^b
Algae	< 5.0	-	-	-	-

2.2. Gadolinium quantification in water and in mussels' soft tissues

Concentrations of Gd in water samples were determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES). Calibration curve (correlation coefficient > 0.999) was obtained with 5 standards prepared from successive dilutions of a multi-elemental standard (IV-ICPMS 71A). The quantification limit was established as the lower standard of the calibration curve ($5.0 \mu\text{g/L}$), and an acceptable coefficient of variation among replicates of 5% was considered.

For the determination of Gd concentrations in mussels' soft tissues microwave assisted acid digestion of samples was carried out before quantification by ICP-OES. Circa 200 mg of freeze-dried biomass was placed in Teflon tubes with HNO_3 65%, H_2O_2 30% and ultrapure water in a 1:2:1 mL proportion. Tubes were then placed in a microwave at 160°C for 10 min. After cooling, samples were collected into 25 mL tubes and the volume made up with ultrapure water. Digestion cycles followed a complete quality control procedure, including sample duplicates, blanks (Teflon tubes with HNO_3 , H_2O_2 and ultrapure water) and certified reference material (Pinto et al., 2019). Limit of quantification was $0.6 \mu\text{g/g}$, dry weight.

2.3. Biochemical markers

Biomarkers were determined in mussels' whole soft tissues. For each condition, energy-related (glycogen content – GLY; electron transport system activity – ETS) and oxidative stress (superoxide dismutase activity – SOD; catalase activity – CAT; glutathione reductase activity – GRed; lipid peroxidation levels – LPO; protein carbonylation levels – PC) biomarkers were assessed. Different buffers were used for different biomarkers, with 0.5 g FW of soft tissue for each buffer (Coppola et al., 2017).

2.3.1. Energy related biomarkers

It has been demonstrated that organisms' metabolic capacity and their energy reserves content may be altered by the exposure to stressful conditions, namely the presence of pollutants (Coppola et al., 2017;

Henriques et al., 2019; Monteiro et al., 2019). Cellular respiration in organisms is conducted through a chain of enzymes called ETS located in the mitochondrial inner membrane, being the activity of this chain of enzymes a biochemical measure of organisms' potential metabolic capacity (García-Martín et al., 2014; Gosling, 2003; Lampert, 1984; Ortman and Grieshaber, 2003). In the present study the metabolic capacity was assessed by measuring the ETS activity, following Packard (1974) method, with modifications done by De Coen and Janssen (1997). The final reaction product was read at an absorbance of 490 nm with intervals of 25 s during 10 min. The amount of formazan formed was calculated using an extinction coefficient of $15.900/(\text{mol/L})/\text{cm}$ and results were expressed in nmol per min per g FW.

Glycogen is a storage form of glucose, being an important fuel reserve source of energy for sudden energetic activity. The released glucose can provide energy in the absence of oxygen and can thus supply energy for anaerobic activity. For this reason, the GLY content is a reliable measure of organisms' energy expenditure. Thus, in the present study, the energy reserves available for metabolism were determined by quantifying the total GLY content, which was measured following the sulfuric acid (DuBois et al., 1956) method. Glucose standards (0–2 mg/mL) were used. The final reaction of GLY was read at an absorbance of 492 nm. Results were expressed in mg per g FW.

2.3.2. Oxidative stress biomarkers

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are normal products of organisms' cellular aerobic metabolism (Regoli and Giuliani, 2014). Various environmental stresses, including exposure to pollutants, can lead to excessive production of ROS causing progressive oxidative damage (Bojarski et al., 2020). To avoid cellular damage, organisms activate their defence mechanisms, namely increasing the activity of antioxidant enzymes, aiming to eliminate the excess of ROS. Superoxide dismutase enzyme is responsible for the removal of the ROS O_2^- with the consequent formation of H_2O_2 . In order to determine the SOD activity, the Beauchamp and Fridovich (1971) method with adaptations performed by Carregosa et al. (2014) was employed. Standards (0.25–60 U/mL SOD) were used for SOD activity quantification. The determination of SOD activity was

performed through the analysis of samples' absorbance at 560 nm after 20 min of incubation at room temperature. The results were expressed in U per g FW where for SOD one unit (U) of enzyme activity represents a reduction of 50% of nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT). Catalase enzyme, in the presence of Fe^{2+} , converts H_2O_2 in the hydroxy radical (HO^\bullet) through the Fenton reaction. HO^\bullet is an extremely reactive initiator for the lipid peroxidation in the cellular membrane. The activity of CAT was quantified employing the [Johansson and Borg \(1988\)](#) method and the modifications performed by [Carregosa et al. \(2014\)](#). Standards (0–150 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ formaldehyde) were used for CAT activity determination. The final reaction products were measured at an absorbance of 540 nm. Results were expressed in U per g FW where for CAT U is defined as the formation of 1 nmol formaldehyde per min. Glutathione reductase enzyme is responsible for the catalysis of glutathione disulfide (GSSG) to glutathione (GSH). The reduction process is essential for the regulation of glutathione levels in the organism. Glutathione reductase activity was determined according to an adaptation of [Carlberg and Mannervik \(1985\)](#) method, with reading wavelength at 340 nm ($\epsilon = 6.22/(\text{mol/L})/\text{cm}$). The results were expressed in U per g FW where U stands for formation of 1 μmol of NADP^+ per min.

If not successfully eliminated, ROS will induce the peroxidation of the membrane lipids (assessed by LPO) and oxidation of proteins (measured by PC). Among all the peroxidised molecules generated in the LPO process, malondialdehyde (MDA) is one of the most abundant and probably the most commonly used as an oxidative stress marker. The determination of LPO was performed following the method described by [Ohkawa et al. \(1979\)](#). Determinations were performed using the extinction coefficient for Malondialdehyde (MDA) of $1.56 \times 10^5/(\text{mol/L})/\text{cm}$ at 535 nm. Results were expressed in nmol MDA equivalents. Determination of PC levels was performed using the extinction coefficient for DNPH of $22.308/(\text{mol/L})/\text{cm}$ at 450 nm. The results were expressed in nmol of protein carbonyls groups formed per g FW.

2.4. Data analysis

Integrative Biomarker Response (IBR) index was calculated as described by [Beliaeff and Burgeot \(2002\)](#), to assess the potential toxicity of Gd to *M. galloprovincialis*. IBR index is the mean value of each biomarker for each condition (X), general mean (m) and general standard deviation (s) for each biomarker taking into account all conditions; Y and Z values, where $Y = (X - m) / s$ and $Z = Y$ or $-Y$, in the case of activation or inhibition, respectively; S value, calculated as $S = Z + |\text{Min}(Z)|$. Finally, the IBR was calculated as $\text{IBR} = \sum A$, where $A = (\text{Si} + 1)/2$. The IBR calculations were always performed with the same order of parameters for all conditions. All biomarkers measured were used in the calculation of the IBR and they were arranged clockwise in the following order: SOD, CAT, LPO, GLY, GRed, CP and ETS. Values were discussed in terms of a general response given by the final IBR value, where higher values correspond to higher mussels' responsiveness.

The biochemical data (ETS, GLY, LPO, PC, SOD, CAT, GRed) and Gd concentrations obtained from all conditions were submitted to hypothesis testing using permutational multivariate analysis of variance. For this purpose, in order to investigate if the presence of the algae reduces the toxicity of Gd, results obtained from biochemical parameters and Gd quantification in mussels tissues were submitted to PERMANOVA add-on in PRIMER v7 ([Anderson et al., 2008](#)), testing the null hypothesis: no significant differences exist among conditions (CTL, corresponding to mussels in clean seawater, without Gd and in the absence algae; Algae + Mussels, corresponding to mussels with algae in the presence or absence of Gd; Mussels, corresponding to mussels without algae in the presence of Gd). Significance level was established at $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Gadolinium concentrations in seawater and mussels' soft tissues

Gadolinium concentrations in seawater samples are presented in [Table 1](#). Concentrations of Gd in water from **Blanks** showed no significant differences among days 2, 3, 4 and 5, highlighting the chemical stability of the element in seawater during each week of exposure. Gadolinium concentrations in water samples collected from **Mussels** condition (mussels in the presence of Gd) decreased significantly along the week, with the lowest values at the last day of sampling. A similar pattern was observed in water samples collected from **Algae** in the presence of Gd. Among conditions, the highest decrease in Gd concentration along the week was observed in water collected from the condition **Algae + Mussels** in the presence of Gd. No Gd was found in water samples collected from **CTL**, **Algae + Mussels** and **Algae** conditions in the absence of Gd.

Gadolinium content in mussel's soft tissues and the bioconcentration factor (BCF) for each condition is present in [Table 2](#). Gadolinium was found in mussels both in the presence and absence of algae, with significantly lower values in the presence of algae. A similar pattern was observed for BCF factor.

3.2. Biological responses

3.2.1. Mortality

No mortality was observed during the exposure period, so subsequent effects were considered sublethal.

3.2.2. Energy reserves and metabolic capacity

The activity of the electron transport system (ETS) was significantly lower when mussels were exposed to Gd (Mussels condition, [Fig. 1A](#)) in comparison to the remaining conditions. No significant differences were observed among control organisms (CTL) and conditions where mussels were maintained in the presence of algae, with or without Gd.

The glycogen content (GLY) was higher in all test conditions (Algae+Mussels with or without Gd and Mussels conditions) in comparison to CTL mussels ([Fig. 1B](#)).

3.2.3. Antioxidant and biotransformation enzymes

The activity of the antioxidant enzymes (superoxide dismutase, SOD; catalase, CAT; glutathione reductase, GRed) was significantly higher when mussels were exposed to Gd in the presence or absence of algae, in comparison to CTL organisms ([Fig. 2](#)).

3.2.4. Cellular damage and redox balance

Lipid peroxidation (LPO) was significantly higher when mussels were exposed to Gd (both in the presence or absence of algae), in comparison to CTL organisms and mussels with algae but without Gd ([Fig. 3A](#)).

The protein carbonylation (PC) showed no significant differences among conditions ([Fig. 3B](#)).

3.2.5. IBR Index

The IBR index showed the highest value in mussels exposed to Gd in the absence of algae (1.15), followed by mussels exposed to Gd in the presence of algae (0.38). IBR value obtained in mussels only in the presence of algae but without Gd was 0.

3.3. Multivariate analysis

Principle coordinates at horizontal dimension (PCO1) explained 79.1% of total variation, while the PCO vertical dimension (PCO2) explained 13.6% of total variation ([Fig. 4](#)). PCO1 separated mussels exposed to CTL and mussels in the presence of algae but without Gd at the positive side from mussels exposed to Gd, both in the presence and

Table 2

Gadolinium (Gd) concentrations ($\mu\text{g/g}$) in mussels' soft tissues and bioconcentration factor after 21 days of exposure to conditions: **CTL** (clean seawater only with mussels); **Algae + Mussels** (aquaria with algae and mussels in the absence of Gd); **Mussels** (aquaria with mussels without algae in the presence of Gd); **Algae + Mussels** (aquaria with algae and mussels in the presence of Gd). Limit of quantification (LOQ) was $0.6 \mu\text{g/g}$, dry weight. **Gray** conditions represent absence of Gd. **Bold** conditions represent presence of Gd. Significant differences between condition are represented by different lowercase letters. NA = not available.

	Gd concentrations	Bioconcentration
	($\mu\text{g/g}$)	factor
CTL	< 0.60	NA
Algae + Mussels	< 0.60	NA
Mussels	2.2 ± 0.81^a	37^a
Algae + Mussels	0.83 ± 0.13^b	14^b

Fig. 1. A: Electron transport system activity (ETS) and B: glycogen content (GLY) measured in *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. White bars correspond to Gd-free conditions: Control (CTL clean seawater only with mussels); **Algae + Mussels** (aquaria with algae and mussels in the absence of Gd). Black bars represent Gd-exposed conditions: **Mussels** (aquaria with mussels without algae in the presence of Gd); **Algae + Mussels** (aquaria with algae and mussels in the presence of Gd). Significant differences among conditions are represented with different uppercase letters.

absence of algae, in the negative side. High PCO1 correlations were observed for PC and ETS ($r > 0.85$) in the positive side.

4. Discussion

It is well recognized that pollutants discharged in aquatic environments can induce toxic impacts towards marine wildlife (Coppola et al., 2017; Freitas et al., 2020b, 2019; Pagano et al., 2017; Qyli et al., 2020). Among the most commonly described injuries caused by pollutants, namely REEs, organisms' intracellular formation of the so-called reactive oxygen species (ROS) has been described, which can impair organisms' oxidative status (Freitas et al., 2020a). Under non-stressful conditions, ROS are naturally produced during several cellular pathways of aerobic metabolism, including oxidative phosphorylation and electron transport chains in mitochondria and microsomes (Regoli and Giuliani, 2014). Under stressful conditions, the overproduction of ROS usually causes an alteration of the cellular balance between prooxidant mechanisms and antioxidant defenses of the target cell, leading to peroxidation of cellular membrane lipids (lipid peroxidation, LPO) and oxidation of proteins (protein carbonylation, PC) (Regoli and Giuliani, 2014). Besides alterations induced in organisms' oxidative status,

pollutants are also responsible for changes on organisms' metabolic capacity with organisms under stressful conditions increasing their metabolic capacity to fuel up defense mechanisms (Freitas et al., 2020b, 2019). Accompanying this increased metabolism, the expenditure of energy reserves can also increase, leading to a decrease on organism's protein, glycogen and lipids content. Nevertheless, under low stress levels organisms may be able to decrease their metabolism to avoid accumulation of pollutants (example: bivalves close their valves and reduce filtration rate), leading to accumulation of energy reserves (Henriques et al., 2019; Pinto et al., 2019).

Gadolinium (Gd) is one of the most commercially exploited REEs, once it is intensely used in the biomedical field as contrast agent in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Its wide employment enhances the risk for this element to be potentially released into the environment, in particular into rivers, lakes and coastal areas through hospital and industrial wastewater or through exhausted devices. This scenario will rise the risks associated with contamination of aquatic environments worldwide. Considering the potential increase of Gd in the aquatic systems and published literature on the impacts of REEs towards marine invertebrate species, the present study evaluated the effects of Gd on *Mytilus galloprovincialis* accumulation levels, oxidative stress levels and

Fig. 2. A: Superoxide dismutase (SOD), B: catalase (CAT) and C: glutathione reductase (GRed) enzymes activities measured in *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. White bars correspond to Gd-free conditions: Control (CTL clean seawater only with mussels); **Algae + Mussels** (aquaria with algae and mussels in the absence of Gd). Black bars represent Gd-exposed conditions: **Mussels** (aquaria with mussels without algae in the presence of Gd); **Algae + Mussels** (aquaria with algae and mussels in the presence of Gd). Significant differences among conditions are represented with different uppercase letters.

metabolic capacity, considering the presence and absence of the algae *Ulva lactuca*, a species already described as a good biosorbent of toxic elements (Costa et al., 2020b, 2020a; Ferreira et al., 2020; Henriques et al., 2015; Pinto et al., 2020). The present findings do not only contribute to the understanding of REEs impacts towards marine wildlife but also reveals the role of algae in preventing injuries, generating

not only new insights on water remediation and safety, but also highlighting the potential for resources recovery. Previous studies already proved the application of living macroalgae as a simple and effective alternative technology for removing and recovering other REEs from water (Ferreira et al., 2020; Jacinto et al., 2018).

In accordance with previous studies that revealed the impacts that REEs induced in bivalves, the present study demonstrated the negative effects of Gd on oxidative stress and metabolic capacity of the mussel species *M. galloprovincialis*. The impacts induced were clearly associated with Gd accumulation levels, with the co-exposure of Algae + Mussels to Gd being less harmful than mussels exposed to Gd in the absence of the algae. In particular, the present study revealed that after the exposure period, mussels exposed to Gd accumulated this element in significantly lower concentrations when in the presence of algae. BCF was also significantly lower when mussels were exposed to Gd in the presence of *U. lactuca*. Although previous studies demonstrated the capacity of bivalves to accumulate Gd (Hanana et al., 2017; Henriques et al., 2019), the present results are innovative since clearly indicate that the algae removed Gd from the seawater, decreasing Gd accumulation in mussels, which led to lower Gd concentrations in mussels' tissues when contamination occurred in the presence of algae. These results are corroborated by the decreasing of Gd concentrations observed in the water where algae were present. Previous studies developed by Ferreira et al. (2020) already demonstrated that *U. lactuca* has higher capacity to remove Gd from the water in comparison to *Fucus spiralis* (Phaeophyta) and *Gracilaria sp.* (Rhodophyta). Although all species were able to accumulate Gd from seawater with 10, 157, and 500 $\mu\text{g/L}$, the green and red macroalgae performed better, following the order: green > red > brown. Removal efficiencies reached 85%. These authors revealed that the high surface area of *U. lactuca* provides a large contact surface with the solution, with plenty of binding sites, which facilitates the removal of Gd. Furthermore, these authors highlighted that the type, distribution and availability of functional groups onto macroalgae surface have a major influence, which explains the removal capability of *U. lactuca*. The uptake of Gd was also pointed out by the authors as a possible mechanism that can occur mainly by sorption on the surface of the algae.

Gadolinium toxicity appears to be associated with its action as a blocker of calcium channels, as its ionic radius is nearly equal to that of divalent Ca^{2+} (Sherry et al., 2009), competing in physiological processes requiring Ca (e.g., muscle contraction, mineralization, cell division; Walker, 1988). In particular, Martino et al. (2018) studying the effects of Gd in sea urchins demonstrated a reduction in the Ca amount in parallel with an increase in the Gd content, showing that the disruption of spicule formation is likely to be due to the action of Gd as a blocker of calcium channels, affecting biomineralization. Nevertheless, still scarce information exists regarding Gd toxicity, in particular in bivalves. In freshwater mussels *Dreissena polymorpha* Gd exposure triggers mitochondrial and anti-inflammatory pathways (Hanana et al., 2017), while in the marine mussel *M. galloprovincialis* Gd induced metabolic alterations and oxidative stress (Henriques et al., 2019). The present study showed that the highest Gd concentrations observed in mussels' tissues when in the absence of algae (Mussels condition) was accompanied by lower metabolic capacity recorded at this condition. These findings are in agreement with previous studies that already demonstrated the capacity of bivalves to reduce their metabolism when in the presence of pollutants, in an attempt to avoid the accumulation of substances by limiting their filtration rate. In particular, studies conducted by Almeida et al. (2014a, 2014b) demonstrated the capacity of *Ruditapes philippinarum* clams to reduce their clearance rate and metabolic capacity at the highest tested drug concentrations. Also Duquesne et al. (2004) observed a reduction in *Macoma balthica* clearance rate as an effort to limit the exposure to metal contamination, which led to a slowdown in metabolism and a relatively stable GLY concentration. Lower metabolic capacity was also revealed by Henriques et al. (2019) in *M. galloprovincialis* mussels exposed to different Gd concentrations (15, 30, 60 and 120 $\mu\text{g/L}$) for 28 days. Also Pinto et al. (2019) studying the

Fig. 3. A: Lipid peroxidation (LPO) and B: protein carbonylation (PC) levels measured in *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. White bars correspond to Gd-free conditions: Control (CTL clean seawater only with mussels); **Algae + Mussels** (aquaria with algae and mussels in the absence of Gd). Black bars represent Gd-exposed conditions: **Mussels** (aquaria with mussels without algae but in the presence of Gd); **Algae + Mussels** (aquaria with algae and mussels in the presence of Gd). Significant differences among conditions are represented with different uppercase letters.

Fig. 4. Centroids ordination diagram (PCO) based on Gd concentrations in mussels' soft tissues and biochemical parameters, measured in *M. galloprovincialis* exposed to different conditions. Pearson correlation vectors are superimposed as supplementary variables, namely biochemical data ($r > 0.75$): Gd, ETS, GLY, SOD, CAT, GRed, LPO, PC. Gray conditions represent the absence of Gd (CTL; **Algae + Mussels**); Black conditions represent the presence of Gd (**Mussels**; **Algae + Mussels**).

effects of other REE (lanthanum, La) in the same species showed decreased electron transport system (ETS) activity in La exposed mussels (0.1, 1.0 and 10 mg/L) in comparison to non-contaminated ones. Nevertheless, Perrat et al. (2017) reported no ETS alterations in *D. rostriformis bugensis* and *Corbicula fluminea* employing lower concentrations (1–10 µg/L) of Gd-based contrast agent gadoteric acid (Gd-DOTA). Such results may thus indicate that higher REE bioavailability and higher accumulated concentrations are required in order to cause variations in bivalves' metabolism.

Regarding mussels' energy reserves, in particular glycogen (GLY) content, the present findings highlight the capacity of *M. galloprovincialis* to prevent their expenditure under adverse conditions, in particular under Gd exposure. The decrease of GLY expenditure is most probably associated with lower metabolism observed in mussels exposed to Gd, namely in the absence of algae, which resulted into lower energy reserves consumption. Previous studies demonstrated similar responses of bivalves exposed to Gd (Henriques et al., 2019) or other metals, such as mercury (Coppola et al., 2017), or even in bivalves collected in a highly polluted environment (Chiesa et al., 2018).

Studies employing marine (Pinto et al., 2019; Mestre et al., 2019)

and freshwater (Perrat et al., 2017; Blinova et al., 2018) species, already demonstrated alterations on the oxidative status due to REEs. In the present study, the results obtained clearly demonstrated that under Gd exposure mussels were forced to activate their antioxidant defenses, increasing the activity of the enzymes superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and glutathione reductase (GRed), which was particularly clear in SOD when mussels were exposed to Gd in the absence of algae. Such results corroborated the fact that the presence of algae may diminish Gd risks to mussels by decreasing the amount of the element in water, thus limiting Gd accumulation and the need for antioxidant defenses activation. Published literature already demonstrated that bivalves were able to increase their defense mechanisms in the presence of pollutants, namely REEs. In particular, Henriques et al. (2019); Pinto et al. (2019); Freitas et al. (2020a) reported an increase in SOD, CAT and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) enzymes after exposure of *M. galloprovincialis* to the REE Gd, La and Dysprosium (Dy), respectively.

When overproduced and not efficiently eliminated by antioxidant mechanisms, ROS may induce the peroxidation of the membrane lipids. Among all the peroxidized molecules generated in the LPO process, malondialdehyde (MDA) is one of the most abundant and probably the

most commonly used as an oxidative stress marker (Regoli and Giuliani, 2014; Regoli et al., 2011). Protein carbonylation is an oxidative stress biomarker as well, resulting from the oxidation of proteins by ROS and corresponding to the presence of carbonyl groups, such as aldehydes and ketones, in specific amino acid side chains such as lysine, proline, arginine and threonine (Mesquita et al., 2014). In the present study, Gd exposed mussels were subjected to increasing cellular damage, associated with higher LPO levels, although being able to maintain their PC levels. These results indicated that the antioxidant defenses triggered by mussels were not enough to avoid peroxidation of the membrane lipids although preventing the occurrence of PC. Henriques et al. (2019) also demonstrated that mussels exposed to Gd showed higher LPO levels than control organisms, although the activation of antioxidant defense mechanisms. Similarly, *M. galloprovincialis* exposed to the Dy showed higher LPO levels, although SOD and CAT activity were increased along the exposure gradient (Freitas et al., 2020a).

Considering the general biochemical response of mussels, values obtained from the IBR clearly demonstrated that the most stressful condition was the exposure to Gd in the absence of algae, corroborating the role of algae to limit risks due to Gd. Also the PCO analyses demonstrated that biochemical performance of mussels in the absence of Gd (both with or without algae) differed from the biochemical responses that characterized the answer of mussels exposed to Gd (regardless the presence or not of algae).

5. Conclusions

The present study highlighted the toxicity of Gd but revealed the capacity of *U. lactuca* to prevent injuries provoked by this REE to *M. galloprovincialis*. The results herein presented are innovative and will advance the state of the art not only regarding the effects of REEs, but also recognizing the role of algae in the protection of other aquatic organisms.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Giacomo Trapasso: Bibliographic search, data analyses, ms writing and editing, Francesca Coppola, Vanessa Queirós, Bruno Henriques: Laboratory work, data analyses, Rosa Freitas, Amadeu M.V.M. Soares, Stefania Chiesa, Eduarda Pereira: supervision of data analyses, paper editing and revision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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